

Design of Mobile Web-Based Island Tourism Marketing Information System Using SDLC (System Development Life Cycle) (September 2021)

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Abstract— The geographical condition of Sungai Pisang Village located on the coastal fringe and not too far from the famous island tourism which potential in West Sumatera becomes an opportunity for the people of Sungai Pisang, especially the fishermen to increase their standard of living. But in reality, the outsiders in the Bungus area are more likely to take advantage of the opportunity because of their location close to the city center. The tourists can only be seen from far by biduk fishermen of Sungai Pisang. Most tourists prefer to use Tour and Travel services from Bungus area. Biduk fishermen are only bringing few tourists to the island tour even though the price offered is much cheaper. Based on preliminary study, there are problems such as the lack of knowledge of the fisherman on the effective product marketing strategy. So far, there are no marketing tools to promote the transportation services of biduk fisherman for the island tourism in the Sungai Pisang broadly. Therefore, it is necessary to design a marketing information system of island tourism biduk. The marketing information system is a mobile web-based designed using PHP programming language and supported by the MySQL database. The information marketing system is expected to increase the number of tourists who use the island tourism biduk as an effort to increase the sustainable fishermen's economy.

Keyword: Analysis, Fisherman's Dipper, Information Systems, Marketing Strategy, Web Mobile

I. INTRODUCTION

An information system is a computer-based system that provides information to multiple users with similar needs. The users are usually incorporated in a formal organizational entity, such as a department or institution of a government agency that can be spelled out into a field directorate, part up to the smallest unit below. Information describes the organization or one of its main systems about what has happened in the past, what is happening now and what may happen in the future about the organization. Information contains a meaning that is data that has been processed into a form that has more meaning and can be used for decision making. Data are facts that represent 3 circumstances, conditions, or events that occur or exist within or in the physical environment of the organization ^[1].

Computer-based information systems use computer technology to process data into meaningful information, there is a fairly sharp difference between computers and computer programs on the one hand with information systems on the

other. The computers and computer software available are the technical foundations, tools, and materials of modern information systems. Computers can be used to store and process information. A computer program or computer software is a set of operating instructions that direct and control the processing of information.

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Today, the information systems used are more focused on computer-based information systems. The hope to be obtained in such information systems is that by using information technology or computer-based information systems, the information generated can be more accurate, qualified, and timely. However, at this time we can still see that there are some remote areas that have not felt how the information was obtained quickly and accurately. This is certainly very influential for people's lives such as Sungai Pisang fishermen. Sungai Pisang fishermen have the main job of sailing, besides they have a side job by delivering tourists to the island of Pasumpahan, but the fishermen do not so much have passengers because the tourists prefer to use tour and travel services because they can access via mobile ^[2].

Therefore, the problems of the fishermen above are very important to be solved with Modern System Analysis and Design. The development of information systems for fishermen in Sungai Pisang can be done by applying the SLDC (System Development Life Cycle) system using PHP and supported by MySQL database. With the development of information systems through web-based mobile, this is expected to improve the economy of banana river fishermen ^[3].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter will discuss about system analysis and design, system development life cycle (SDLC), rapid application development (RAD), computer aided software engineering (CASE), agile methodology and extreme programming, object-oriented analysis and design (OOAD), and rational unified processes (RUP).

2.1 System Analysis and Design

System analysis is a term that collectively describes the early phases of system development. System analysis is a problem-solving technique that outlines components by learning how well they work and interact to achieve their goals. System analysis is the earliest stage of system development that becomes the foundation in determining the success of the information system produced later ^[4].

System design is a complementary problem-solving technique that lifts back component parts into a complete system, hoping for an improved system. This saw additions, deletions, and changes in relative parts of the initial system. In the design of models and data models, to realize the needs of the system defined and the framework for coding is also determined. Documentation of this design stage will be very useful for future system development, if there is a change in the user's needs.

2.2 System Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

In software development certainly passes several stages of development, ranging from planning to implementation. When the software or system has been implemented in its development there are problems related to the system. This cycle is called the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) ^[5]. Systems Development Life Cycle is a common methodology used to develop information systems.

The life cycle of information system development is a form used to describe the main stages and steps at that stage in the system development process. The development of a new system or its development will start from the planning stage again. The following is an explanation of the life cycle of system development:

2.2.1 Planning

System development planning basically aims to know and put forward the system to be developed. What targets are achieved, the length of work, and consider the needs of funds used in the development of the system.

2.2.2 Analysis

At this stage of analysis collect the needs of any business from various stakeholders concerned. Define the needs of the business that will be followed up to be accommodated by the system to be built. Make a simple prototype to meet these needs. Prioritizing the needs of the business that have been defined. Create and evaluate alternative solutions for each of these needs. Review solution recommendations with management.

2.2.3 Design

Design by integrating it with the network. Design the application architecture to be used. Design a screen view for the user. Designing system interfaces. Design and integrate systems with databases. Make a prototype for the details of the design. Create and integrate the system with the control system.

2.2.4 Implementation

Build software components. Verify and test the completed system. Convert data. Train users to interact and complete their work tasks using the system. Create documentation against the system that has been built in the form of a manual book.

2.2.5 Activity

Perform system maintenance by checking periodically / periodically.

2.3 Rapid Application Development (RAD)

Rapid Application Development (RAD) is a term originally used to describe the software development process first developed and successfully used during the mid-1970s by the New York Telephone Co. development center system under the direction of Dan Gielan. RAD is essentially a variation of the sequential release strategy. It is also very important to note that some technology suppliers claim that advanced development environments such as high programming languages, application development devices, and supporting technologies (CASE) ^[6].

2.4 Computer Aided Software Engineering (CASE)

The diagram tool allows graphical representation. Computer displays and reported generators help prototype how the system "looks and feels". IBM Rational Products is the most well-known CASE tool. Analytics tools automatically check consistency in diagrams, forms, and reports. The central repository provides integrated storage of diagrams, reports, and project management specifications Documentation generators standardize technical and user documentation ^[7]. Code generators allow automatic generation of programs and database code directly from design documents, diagrams, forms, and reports.

2.5 Agile Methodology and Extreme Programming

Agile is a term used to describe a software development approach that emphasizes gradual delivery, team collaboration, continuous planning, and continuous spending, instead of trying to deliver it all at once toward the end ^[8]. Agile focuses on maintaining a streamlined process and creating viable beverage products (MVP) that go through a number of iterations before everything is final. Agile methodology is a practice that promotes continuous iterations of development and testing throughout the project's software development cycle.

2.6 Object Oriented Analysis and Design (OOAD)

Object orientation programming works well when coupled with object-oriented analysis and design process. Object orientation is a technique in software development This technique is the culmination point in determining how to effectively build a system and becomes the most popular method used by software developers today. The object presents something real system such as student, aircraft wing surface control system, sensor or engine. Objects also present

something in the form of concepts such as bank customers, trademarks, weddings or just listings. A class is a picture of a set of objects that have attributes, characters and conditions. Classes are similar to data types in non-object programming, but are more comprehensive because they have both structure and characteristics.

2.7 Rational Unified Processes (RUP)

RUP is strongly influenced by the analysis and design of objects and UML ^[9]. In 2003, IBM acquired Rational Software. There are three perspectives at the RUP: Dynamic Perspective and Lifecycle Phases, Static Perspective, and Practice Perspective and Core Process. Dynamic Perspective and Lifecycle Phases show the phases of RUP over time that are constantly changing. Static Perspective, and Practice Perspective are made of things that don't change themselves to keep working to change dynamic processes. Practice Perspective is created from effective implementations based on good previous experience used during the process.

III. DISCUSSION

The design of the island's tourism dipper marketing information system is more focused on developing mobile websites. The design of the mobile website is done by implementing a system development life cycle. SLDC serves to develop, maintain, and replace information systems.

3.1 Planning

At this stage, various kinds of designs are carried out, such as database system design, marketing information system design, and strategy design. In addition to various kinds of design, another thing that is done is designing the mobile web.

The design of a mobile website for booking tourist dippers on the banana river is used php programming language and supported MySQL database. The design of this marketing information system is expected to increase the number of tourists using island tourism dippers as an effort to improve the economy of the big dipper fishermen.

3.2 Analysis

The analysis in this case is to analyze the needs carried out in the implementation of activities such as observations, data collection and information related to the design of the island tourism dipper marketing information system. The marketing information system designed must be user friendly so as not to confuse users in looking for the information needed.

3.3 Design

At the time of designing a mobile web for banana island tourism dippers, data related to island tourism in the Banana River was collected and stored in a database designed using MySQL. These databases are used in designed marketing information systems. To access the island's travel dipper marketing information system, it can be opened on browsers such as Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome and Opera, by typing

biduakayah.com. The island tourism dipper marketing information system has several menus for the choice of tourist islands. Each tourist island comes with its own package price.

In addition to the price information of island tour packages, the island's tourism dipper marketing information system is equipped with pictures of the beauty of each of these tourist islands to attract visitors. This marketing information system is also equipped with a location map from google map to make it easier for users to find the desired tourist island location. After getting information about the desired island tour, users can contact the dipper fishermen through the contact number available either by phone, message, or email. The design of the mobile web-based island tourism marketing information system can support marketing and promotional activities by updating information about island tour packages, attractions on the tourist island, tourist schedules, and tourist promos.

3.4 Implementation

At the implementation stage, the following activities are:

1. Transfer of the website from localhost to server hosting.
2. Creation of a database on hosting and application of user access rights on the database.
3. Application testing and repair (debugging).

Furthermore, the operation of the marketing information system is carried out by dipper fishermen as admins who are trained to be able to operate marketing information systems effectively. With the training of the use of information systems marketing island tourism dippers to fishermen, it is expected that the number of tourists increases so that the fishermen's economy also improves.

3.5 Maintenance

Maintenance is needed in the information system because it aims to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of existing system performance. In addition, maintenance system analysis is also needed so that the use of tools or systems can last a long time. In this journal, we must make periodic updates to the mobile web so that the mobile web can attract tourists using this mobile web.

IV. CONCLUSION

This journal designed the marketing information system of island tourism dippers for big dipper fishermen in Sungai Pisang, Padang, West Sumatra. This marketing information system is designed using the PHP programming language and is supported by MySQL databases. The stages carried out are needs analysis, database system design, information system design, validation, and implementation. This mobile web-based island tourism marketing information system provides information on island tour packages consisting of Pasumpahan island, Sirandah island, Pagang island, Pamutusan island, and Suwarnadwipa. In addition to displaying images of the beauty of the tourist island, this marketing information system is also equipped with a location map to facilitate users. The design of this marketing information system is expected to increase the number of tourists using island tourism dippers as an effort to improve the economy of sustainable big dipper fishermen.

V. REFERENCE

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